

JAMES BAYNES

(1766-1837)

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CURATORIAL INTRODUCTION

The period known as late Georgian corresponds to the final years of the reigns of King George III (1738-1820) and George IV (1762-1830), the latter acted as Regent during the last period of madness of George III from 1811 to 1820; he was a member of the nobility and patron of the arts and also a well-known libertine.

The artists of this period worked and developed their art with the intention of preserving the popular imagery of earlier times, focusing mainly on the neoclassical whilst also responding to the growing popularity of romanticism.

During this period, the artists benefited from the change of status of the artist, the growing wealth of the middle classes in an increasingly industrialised society rapidly increased the demand for art. This time also saw the formation of many art groups and societies which presented their own exhibitions. This opened the way for artists and collectors to talk directly leading to an affordable art market for the British middle classes and putting the artists in direct competition with commercial galleries.

It was a pivotal moment in the expansion of the art market with a direct dialogue between the artists and the rapidly growing middle classes now with disposable income for such refinements as art. Art materials were also being developed in tandem with great advances permitting a wider offering, dimensionally different works, and pigments of higher quality and colour consistency.

James Baynes was an English artist born in Lancaster in 1766, he entered the Royal Academy at the age of 18 supported by a number of patrons, quickly earning a good reputation in the Academy and becoming a Drawing Master. He lost his financial support when he married without the consent of his patrons. Baynes continued his career by working for the Polygraphic Society which made reproductions of well-known works of art and retouched

them by hand. His work earned him financial independence and he was able to live in Central London for more than 40 years, until his death.

The pieces that we present in the exhibition are a private collection passed down directly through the artist's family for around 200 years, until today. We were fortunate to be able to acquire this collection directly from the family. Therefore this is a collection that has never been seen outside the artist's family and friendship circle, before now. These pencil and ink drawings are exhibited here in Mexico City for the first time, we will be the first to be able to appreciate the complete collection curated and presented together, the hand of a Drawing Master from two centuries ago. An unrepeatable experience.

Dr. Pablo Angel Lugo

Marzo 2021

ABOUT THE COLLECTION

It is rare to discover previously hidden works of great skill and value and even more so a complete collection which has remained in the family of an artist for generations.

Being myself a collector of early English watercolours and drawings, I am always scouring the auction catalogues for interesting lots, this has become an opportunity and a challenge in Covid times, not being able to see items physically means taking more of a chance, but also deters other buyers. And so this is how I managed to acquire the James Baynes collection, the works were presented without fanfare in a cardboard box in the corner of a regional auctioneers general sale, almost hidden from public view. I knew that James Baynes was an artist of some reputation but it was still a great surprise and very exciting to unpack the lot and really see the exquisite skill in this unique collection. Clearly the works of the Drawing Master that Baynes was.

The labelling on the reverse of the works confirmed that the collection had been in James Baynes's family for generations, and so hidden from public view for 200 years.

John Wright, UK Director
Glocal Art Markets

JAMES BAYNES (1766-1837)

James Baynes was a watercolour artist and drawing master, he was born in Kirkby Lonsdale, Westmorland as the son of a tradesman and the eldest of six children. He showed early promise as an artist and was employed to draw heads and works devices, his talent was recognised by Dr Campbell a local physician who sent some of his sketches to the painter George Romney, Baynes was then sent to London to study under George Romney at the expense of Dr Campbell. In 1784 he became a student of the Royal Academy. His marriage in 1785 was not approved by Dr Campbell and so he forfeited his patronage.

He taught drawing with many notable pupils such as John Wood, Sir Henry Sass and J D Harding. He was a constant exhibitor of watercolours and occasionally oils at the Royal Academy from 1796 until 1837. His subject matter concentrated on Norfolk, North Wales, Cumberland and Kent, often introducing figures and cattle. His son Thomas Mann Baynes was also a noted artist.

He fathered eight children and was a member of the Sandemanian Church, a fundamentalist Christian faith, he travelled extensively to Southern England in 1802, Wales and the West of England in 1810, Cumberland in 1815 and Kent in 1816.

Baynes's works are held in the UK Government Art Collection, Rhode Island School of Design Collection, The British Museum in London, Museum of Fine Arts, Boston, the Yale Center for British Art, the Museum of New Zealand and private collections.

Alder and Thorn

1820 *ca.*

211 x 127 mm

Pencil on paper, 150 g/m²

The Old Barn

1820 *ca.*

315 x 215 mm

Pencil on paper, 200 g/m²

Ash

1820 *ca.*

190 x 112 mm

Monochromatic watercolour and pencil on paper, 200 g/m²

Sheerness

1820 *ca.*

169 x 118 mm

Watercolour and pencil on paper, 200 g/m²

Engraving

1820 *ca.*

325 x 199 mm

Pencil on paper, 200 g/m²

Foliage

1820 *ca.*

185 x 127 mm

Pencil on paper, 200 g/m²

House on the Country Road

1820 *ca.*

302 x 197 mm

Ink and pencil on paper, 200 g/m²

Knotted Tree

1820 *ca.*

120 x 190 mm

Pencil on paper, 200 g/m²

Sheep sketches

1820 *ca.*

145 x 99 mm

Pencil on paper, 200 g/m²

Shoreline

1820 *ca.*

281 x 194 mm

Pencil on paper, 200 g/m²

Thatched Cottage

1820 *ca.*

182 x 131 mm

Pencil on paper, 200 g/m²

The Cottage

1820 *ca.*

313 x 214 mm

Pencil on paper, 200 g/m²

The Herdsman

1820 *ca.*

167 x 85 mm

Pencil on paper, 150 g/m²

Cattle Grazing

1820 *ca.*

222 x 147 mm

Pencil and chalk on paper, 100 g/m²

The Old Stone Cottage

1820 *ca.*

182 x 131 mm

Pencil on paper, 150 g/m²

Archway in Stone Wall
1820 *ca.*
350 x 246 mm
Pencil on paper, 150 g/m²

Mother & Daughter Under The Ash Tree

1820 *ca.*

288 x 213 mm

Ink and pencil on paper, 150 g/m²

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